

Biomass Power Plant in Brazil: a financial analysis using FINPLAN

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1. Introduction

Since the world is undergoing an energy transition, countries need to make their energy production cleaner to help achieve global emissions reduction goals. Brazil stands out as one of the most crucial players in this transition, with approximately 80% of its electric energy produced from clean sources such as hydropower, solar, wind farms and biomass [1]. Notably, the country holds the title of the world's leading producer of sugarcane ethanol, offering substantial potential for biomass energy production through the combustion of its byproducts, such as sugarcane bagasse.

According to Davis, 2024 [2] and BRAZIL, 2023 [3], Brazil has the potential to achieve 15% of its electricity generation through Biomass Power Plants, but the current contribution stands at around 4.7%, as shown in the Figure 01. Given this context, for the purposes of this financial planning analysis, we intend to explore the economic viability of building a medium-sized sugarcane biomass plant in Brazil, specifically in an area with high production of sugarcane bagasse, using the Financial Analysis Model for Electricity Sector Expansion Plans (FINPLAN) [4].

Figure 01: Brazilian Electrical Matrix 2022 [1].

This report is divided into five sections, including this of an introductory nature. In Section 2, the methodology used is presented, the simulated scenarios are described, as well as the sensitivities to be evaluated. In Section 3, the results of the simulations conducted are presented. In Section 4, the results are explored and the obtained political insights are discussed. The conclusions are showed in Section 5.

2. Methodology

2.1 FINPLAN

In this work, the analysis of the feasibility of building the sugarcane bagasse Biomass Power Plant will be carried out using FINPLAN, a financial analysis tool developed by the

International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) for planning and decision making. The model takes into account both local and foreign estimated inflation rates, as well as fluctuations in parity (foreign currency/local currency), financial parameters for loans and equities, and other financial information for a complete financial analysis, with annual profits and losses calculated automatically [4] [5] [6].

Table 01 presents the most important input and output data used in the FINPLAN model.

Table 01: Input and output data of the FINPLAN model.

Input	Output
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Life, construction time, output • Investment & operating expenses • Economic and fiscal parameters (inflation, escalation, exchange rates, taxes) • Financial parameters (credits, bonds, loans, equity, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cash flows • Balance sheet, statement of sources, application of funds • Financial ratios: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working capital ratio • Leverage ratio • Debt repayment ratio • Global ratio • Debt-equity ratio • Etc.

2.2 Biomass Power Plant

In this project, we intend to develop a Biomass Power Plant using sugarcane bagasse with an installed capacity of 200 MW. The construction period is estimated at 6 years, with operations expected to commence in the year 2030. The anticipated lifespan of the plant is 51 years, reaching a maximum annual energy production of 1752 GWh. All relevant financial and economic data for the project can be found in Table 02.

Table 02: Financial and economic data of the project.

Data	
Financial	Economic
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investment needs: 174 million BRL • Sources of financing: 109.5 million BRL as loans and 64.5 million BRL as equity • Interest rate: 8% for 20 years 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Price of electricity for first year: 0.13 BRL/kWh, increasing with inflation • Local inflation: 4.5%, steady rate • Exchange rate USD/BRL: 0.20, reflects inflation rate

2.3 Scenarios

Three simulation scenarios are considered, as described in Table 03. Note that the analysis conducted in this study focuses on evaluating the sensitivity of key financial indicators, namely, the Net Present Value (NPV) project, the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and the Dividends paid to shareholders. This assessment is carried out through variations in the values of three fundamental parameters: Utilization Capacity (UC), Energy Price (EP) and Annual Fuel Cost (AFC).

Table 03: Scenarios and sensitivity analysis.

Scenario	Characteristic	Sensitivity Analysis
1	Decrease in UC (100%, 75%, 250%, 25%)	UC x NPV x IRR UC x Dividend
2	Decrease in EP (0.15, 0.13, 0.11, 0.09 BRL/kWh)	EP x NPV x IRR EP x Dividend
3	Increase in AFC (7, 10, 13, 16 million BRL)	AFC x NPV x IRR AFC x Dividend

3. Results

3.1 Scenario 1

In this first scenario, the utilization capacity of the Biomass Power Plant was assessed at four levels with the aim of evaluating its impact on NPV and IRR. As shown in Figures 02a and 02b, UC is directly proportional to both NPV and IRR, as well as to the Dividend. Also note that the Dividend value with UC equal to 50% is three times smaller when UC is 75%, and six times smaller considering maximum UC.

Note also that the proposal is viable when UC is above 50%, as both the NPV becomes positive, as well as the IRR.

Figure 02: Decrease in Utilization Capacity. (a) UC x NPV x IRR; (b) UC x Dividend.

3.2 Scenario 2

In Scenario 2, the sensitivity of NPV, IRR and Dividend is assessed by varying the value of EP, with UC fixed at 50% for analysis purposes. Analysing Figures 03a and 03b, it can be observed that a decrease in the energy price leads to a reduction in the values of IRR, NPV and Dividends. It can be noticed that the Dividend value, for an EP equal to 0.11 BRL/kWh, remains zero until the year 2052, as the Biomass Power Plant is still paying taxes.

In this case, the proposal is viable when EP is higher than 0.11 BRL/kWh.

Figure 03: Decrease in Energy Price (UC = 50%). (a) EP x NPV x IRR; (b) EP x Dividend.

3.3 Scenario 3

In the last scenario analysis, the AFC is varied at four levels, with UC fixed at 50% for analysis purposes and EP fixed at 0.13 BRL/kWh. Examining Figure 04a, it is observed that an increase in the fuel cost value leads to a reduction in both IRR and NPV, as expected. Simultaneously, the higher the value of AFC, the lower the number of Dividends paid, as shown in Figure 04b. Note that the Dividend value for AFC equal to 13 million USD remains zero until the year 2042, due to loan repayments.

In this case, the proposal is viable when the AFC is lower than 13 million USD.

Figure 04: Increase in Annual Fuel Cost (UC = 50%; EP = 0.13 BRL/kWh). (a) AFC x NPV x IRR; (b) AFC x Dividend.

3.4 General Analysis

Analysing the three scenarios together, it is concluded that the implementation proposal for the Biomass Power Plant using sugarcane bagasse is financially viable for UC above 50%, EC above 0.11 BRL/kWh and AFC below 13 million USD, resulting in Dividends exceeding 180 million USD.

4. Discussion

Sugarcane continues to play a crucial role in the Brazilian economy and presents a unique opportunity for Brazil to lead a global transition in the electricity sector towards more positive environmental outcomes. During the 2022 harvest, Brazil accounted for an impressive 21% of the global sugar production. Projections suggest that the country will maintain its global position, with an anticipated increase of 16% in the next decade [2].

Sugar mills in Brazil adopt a sustainable approach by utilizing 100% of sugarcane bagasse for energy generation, with the excess being fed back into the grid [2]. However, despite this potential, only 4.7% of the viable electrical production from sugarcane is currently being harnessed, even though this source of bioelectricity has the capacity to meet up to 15% of the national demand.

Although there is the Plan Safra, a Brazilian government program aimed at promoting a more sustainable sugarcane industry [2], it is necessary to implement stronger economic policies that address the challenges faced by the country's farmers, providing subsidized credit lines and insurance for agricultural investments.

The results presented in Figures 02, 03 and 04 suggest that UC, EP and AFC have a significant impact on NPV, IRR and the value of Dividends paid.

Although the obtained results have been extensive, it is crucial to emphasize that the FINPLAN model does not conduct an exhaustive analysis of financial criteria, as it is designed to be a supplementary tool in decision-making. In this regard, potential areas for future investigation may include additional sensitivity analyses. This will contribute to gaining a more comprehensive understanding of the financial viability of implementing the Biomass Power Plant using sugarcane bagasse in Brazil. Furthermore, it will assist in making policy decisions to shape the country's future energy and electricity landscape.

Another proposal to deepen the feasibility analysis of the Biomass Power Plant would be the use of Climate, Land-Use, Energy and Water Systems (CLEWs) modelling to assess how the use of biomass will affect agriculture, water and energy in Brazil.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the feasibility of establishing a Biomass Power Plant in Brazil using sugarcane bagasse. Positioned as a strategic initiative for a more sustainable energy matrix, the proposal aims to increase the country's electricity generation from sugarcane bagasse, considering that Brazil has a generation potential approximately three times higher than the production recorded in 2022 (4.7%).

Analysing three scenarios collectively, the study concludes that the proposed Biomass Power Plant implementation is financially viable when the UC exceeds 50%, EC surpasses 0.11 BRL/kWh and AFC remains below 13 million USD. These parameters lead to dividends exceeding 180 million USD, affirming the economic viability of the project.

However, for a successful transition, the Brazilian Government must institute credit lines with more accessible interest rates, recognizing the critical role this form of energy will play against the growing adoption of intermittent renewable sources. Beyond contributing to sustainability, the construction of power plants utilizing sugarcane bagasse biomass holds potential for reinforcing the reliability of the Brazilian electrical system.

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